

Demographic Variables and Choice of Entrepreneurial Skills Among Undergraduates of Universities in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study examined the demographic variables and choice of entrepreneurial skills among undergraduates of Universities in Ekiti State. Specifically, the study examined the difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender; level and course of study. The research design adopted by the researcher was descriptive design of the survey type. The population for the study comprised all undergraduates in public Universities in Ekiti State. The sample consisted of 300 undergraduates selected from two universities in Ekiti State. The sample was selected by the researcher through multi-stage sampling procedure. A self-designed questionnaire tagged Undergraduates' Choice of Entrepreneurial Skill Questionnaire (UCESQ) was used for data collection. The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by experts in Tests and Measurement. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. A coefficient of 0.809 was obtained and this was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable and useful for the study. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender, level and course of

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study. It was recommended among others that gender discrimination in choice of entrepreneurial skills should be discouraged by university management.

Keywords: Demographic Variables, Choice, Entrepreneurial Skills, Undergraduates,

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Introduction

Entrepreneurship can be seen as the process by which a prospective entrepreneur pursues opportunities without regard to the resources that they presently control. This essential means the ability of the entrepreneur to combine all other productions means namely, natural resources, capital and labour to ensure that the business becomes a success (Olagunju, 2004). Agbogidi (2007) further define entrepreneurship as a “process of conceptualizing, organizing, launching and through innovation nurturing a business opportunity into a potential growth venture in a complex and unstable environment”

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financial, psychic, and social risks, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence (Hisrich & Peters, 2009). Essien (2006) sees entrepreneurship as the totality of self-asserting attributes that enable a person to identify latent business opportunities together with the capacity to organize needed resources with which to profitably take advantage of such opportunities in the face of calculated risks and uncertainty. Entrepreneurship is concerned with drive to venture into a business with the readiness to unforeseen risks and so reasonable profit as a reward of such action. Furthermore, entrepreneurship is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investment opportunities, establish and run as enterprises successfully (Jimah, Jimah & Onwuka 2010).

Osinem (2008) opined that skill is an individual's capacity to control elements of behaviour, thinking and feeling within specified contexts and within particular task domains. Mike (2014) asserts that skill acquisition is the ability to be trained on a particular task or function. Equipping undergraduates with different skills in the university will help them to be self-reliant, relevant and functional members of the society whether employed by government or self-employed.

Students' skill acquisition is a powerful tool that can solve the problem of unemployment, meet individual and societal needs (Agu, Chiaha & Ikeme, 2013). Mike (2014) emphasized that the importance of skill acquisition includes self-employment, diverse job opportunities, employment generation, effective function and crime reduction. Equipping university students with different skills is means of taken corrective measures for the high level of unemployment because without skill acquisition the national goals cannot be realized hence corruption and violence will be on increase. Agu, Chiaha and Ikeme (2013) argued that entrepreneurial skills must be nurtured through proper education so that it can be directed to responsible and enriching small business endeavours live.

Leroy, Maes, Sels and Debrulle (2009) have conducted the study on gender effects on entrepreneurial intention among Belgian undergraduates. They suggested that important gender differences in the factors that shape entrepreneurial intentions. There seem to be important distinctions in the defining features of entrepreneurship of men versus women. Men seem to prefer entrepreneurship as a means of getting ahead and see financial restraints and creativity as important practical considerations in their decision to become an entrepreneur. Women seem to prefer entrepreneurship as a means of getting organized and see personal capabilities and know-how as important practical consideration in their decision to become an entrepreneur. Furthermore, women are more inclined to comply with social

pressures than their male counterparts. Further they suggested that different variables may be important to understand what motivates or drives performance of male versus female entrepreneurs (Jones & English, 2004).

Nwachukwu and Chukwunke (2008) have argued in favour of including gender and area of specialization as an explanatory variable while studying entrepreneurs. The findings of these studies lead to realization that the existences of gender differences are real; and such differences are likely to have significant effect on multiple aspects of entrepreneurial activity including success as entrepreneur.

The relevance of entrepreneurial skill motivated the researcher to examine the choice of entrepreneurial skills based on three demographic factors such as gender, level and course of study. Therefore, this study is carried out to examine the demographic variables and choice of entrepreneurial skills among undergraduates of Universities in Ekiti State. The purpose of this study was to examine the demographic variables and choice of entrepreneurial skills among undergraduates of Universities in Ekiti State. Specifically, the study examined:

1. the difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender;
2. the difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level; and
3. the difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender
2. There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level
3. There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study

Methodology

The research design adopted by the researcher was descriptive design of the survey type. The population for the study comprised all undergraduates in public Universities in Ekiti State. The sample consisted of 300 undergraduates selected from two universities in Ekiti State. The sample was selected by the researcher through multi-stage sampling procedure. A self-designed questionnaire tagged Undergraduates' Choice of Entrepreneurial Skill Questionnaire (UCESQ) was used for data collection. It consisted of two sections namely Section A and B. Section A sought for the demographic information of the respondents which included their gender, level and course of study while section B consisted of 15 items which sought for information on the choice of entrepreneurial skills among undergraduates.

The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by experts in Tests and Measurement. The instrument was said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, it claimed to measure. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. A co-efficient of 0.809 was obtained and this was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable and useful for the study. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using frequency counts, means, standard

deviation and percentages. Hypothesis 1 was tested using t-test while hypotheses 2 – 3 were tested using one-way Analysis of Variance at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender

Table 1: t-test analysis for difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Male	132	40.47	3.76	298	0.236	0.813
Female	168	40.37	3.58			

P > 0.05

Table 1 shows that the t-cal value of 0.236 is not significant because the P value (0.813) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level

Groups	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	93.065	3	31.022	2.352	0.072
Within Groups	3903.682	296	13.188		
Total	3996.747	299			

P > 0.05

The result presented in table 2 showed that F-cal value of 2.352 is not significant because the P value (0.072) > 0.05 at 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study

Groups	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	30.866	3	10.289	0.768	0.513
Within Groups	3965.881	296	13.398		
Total	3996.747	299			

P > 0.05

The result presented in table 7 showed that F-cal value of 0.768 is not significant because the P value (0.513) > 0.05 at 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender. The probable reason for this finding could be because male and female students are exposed to the same curriculum contents. Ahmed, Nawaz, Ahmad, Shaukat, Rehman and Ahmed (2010) however find that no significant relationship between gender and the intention to become an entrepreneur. According to some studies conducted by Catley and Hamilton (2008) and Minnit, Arenuis and Langowitz (2005), female and male entrepreneur were found to be equally motivated. The implication of this finding was that no difference existed in the choice of entrepreneurial skills between male and female undergraduates.

The study revealed that there was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level. This implies that undergraduates' level do not determine choice of entrepreneurial skills. In addition, the study revealed that there was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study.

Summary of Findings

- i. There was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender
- ii. There was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their level
- iii. There was no significant difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their course of study

Conclusion

It is concluded that there was no difference in undergraduates' choice of entrepreneurial skills based on their gender, level and course of study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Gender discrimination in choice of entrepreneurial skills should be discouraged by university management.
2. Entrepreneurship education should be introduced by university management from the first year the undergraduates are admitted.
3. Courses on entrepreneurial skills should be made compulsory for all undergraduates irrespective of their course of study.

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